

Identifying and mitigating prescribing errors in outpatient clinics: a prospective analysis of pharmacist interventions and clinical outcomes

Derar H. Abdel-Qader¹

¹ Faculty of Pharmacy and Medical Sciences, University of Petra, Amman, Jordan

² Department of Pharmacy Practice and Pharmacotherapeutics, College of Pharmacy, University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates

³ Department of Applied Pharmaceutical Sciences, School of Pharmacy, Isra University, Amman, Jordan

Corresponding author: Derar H. Abdel-Qader (d.balawi@igec.com.au)

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Abstract

Background: Although prescribing errors (PEs) are a major threat to patient safety in primary care, there is a scarcity of data on their occurrence and nature in Jordanian primary care.

Objectives: This study aimed to investigate the incidence, types, severity, and predictors of PEs in Jordanian primary healthcare, as well as the nature and outcomes of pharmacist interventions.

Method: This was a prospective observational study conducted in 12 community pharmacies across Jordan over 12 weeks.

Results: Of the 617 patients included, 102 experienced PEs, resulting in a total of 165 erroneous medication orders. The overall incidence rates of PEs and patients with errors were 14.9% and 16.5%, respectively. The most common erroneous therapeutic category was antibiotics (24.8%), followed by analgesics (14.5%). The most common type of PE was wrong drug (33.33%), followed by omission errors (25.52%) and wrong dose (17.19%). The least common type was wrong duration (10.94%). Of the 192 PEs identified, nine (4.69%) were deemed lethal, 42 (21.88%) severe, and 75 (39.06%) moderate in severity. The most common dosage form for patients with errors was tablets (55.7%). The total number of pharmacist interventions was 216, of which 66.7% were process-based and 33.3% outcome-based. Among these interventions, 75.0% were fully accepted by patients and 68.5% were fully approved by physicians.

Conclusion: Overall, PEs in primary care were common and could cause severe harm. Wrong drug, omission, and wrong dose were the most frequent types of PEs. Pharmacist interventions were crucial and fell into two major categories: process-based and outcome-based.

Keywords

incidence, Jordan, pharmacist, prescribing errors, primary care, severity, types

Introduction

Prescribing errors (PEs) are defined as any deviation from an acceptable and safe prescription that might include errors in dosage, frequency, route of administration, or medication selection resulting in hospitalization, disability, or even death for patients (Dean et al. 2000).

Even though PEs pose significant harm to patients in primary care, there has been insufficient research carried out on their nature and frequency, especially in low- and middle-income countries. This lack of data poses an unacceptable barrier for healthcare providers and policymakers seeking solutions that effectively prevent or manage PEs.

Jordan lacks research relating to PEs in primary care; however, a study conducted in secondary care revealed high rates of PEs due to communication breakdown. Abdel-Qader et al. (2020a) investigated PEs in Jordanian hospitals and found a high incidence of errors with relatively concerning severity. These results imply that PEs are also likely an issue within the primary healthcare sector in Jordan, thus mandating further study in this field.

Jordan's community pharmacies face several difficulties associated with PE research. At its core is an insufficient knowledge base about their incidence and impact on patient safety; this lack of data makes identifying effective prevention or management strategies even harder for healthcare providers and policymakers (Basheti et al. 2021). Thus, the aim of this study was to investigate the incidence, types, severity, and predictors of PEs in primary care in Jordan, as well as the nature and outcomes of pharmacist interventions.

Materials and methods

Study design

A prospective observational study was conducted in 12 community pharmacies to collect real-world information on PEs intercepted in community pharmacies. By closely observing and documenting errors in these settings, insights into their frequency, types, and pharmacist interventions were gained. Community pharmacists collected data over an agreed-upon period by carefully observing PEs based on predefined criteria and classifying them according to predefined rules.

Comprehensive details regarding study objectives, data collection process, and potential benefits associated with participation were provided to research community pharmacists. At the initial contact meeting with pharmacists, the principal investigator provided induction training on the data collection and classification procedure and stressed the confidential and anonymous nature of any collected data, as well as ethical considerations, which were approved by the University of Petra's Research Ethics Committee (O/2/8/2023).

Study flow and settings

A semi-structured data collection form was devised based on an extensive review of existing literature (Overhage and Lukes 1999; Abdel-Qader et al. 2020b; Dean 2000) and current pharmacy practices in Jordan. To ensure content validity, a multidisciplinary expert committee was formed, consisting of a clinical pharmacist, an internal medicine physician, and a health communication specialist. Members were selected based on their expertise in prescribing practices, patient care, and healthcare communication. This committee evaluated the form's relevance and appropriateness in measuring the desired variables. Following this validation, a pilot phase was conducted to assess the feasibility and applicability of the data collection form in a real-life environment by employing three pharmacies. Their feedback was carefully considered during refinements to the form. After the successful pilot study, 12 community pharmacies (26 pharmacists) were recruited for participation in the full-scale data collection phase over 3 months (March to May 2023).

Sample size

To calculate the sample size for documenting PEs, the following formula was employed: $n = (Z^2 \times P \times (1 - P)) / e^2$. By considering the desired confidence level of 95% (Z-score of 1.96), the PE rate of 12.5% according to a previous study conducted by Abdel-Qader et al. (2020a), and the margin of error (e) as 2%, the required sample size was 1052 medications.

Participants

To achieve the required sample size of 1052 medications for this study, a purposive sampling methodology was employed. This involved the strategic selection of 12 pharmacies: six from the Central Region, four from the North, and two from the South. This approach was deemed most appropriate because it enabled the deliberate selection of pharmacies based on their geographic region, which corresponded to areas defined by population connectivity and distance, and their anticipated prescription volume. Purposive sampling ensured that representative data could be gathered from across Jordan's diverse primary healthcare landscape, while also accommodating the practical limitations and logistical constraints inherent in conducting research across a geographically dispersed area.

Pharmacies were included in the study based on several key criteria. Firstly, to ensure a sufficient quantity of medication data for analysis, participating pharmacies needed to receive a minimum of 10 prescriptions per day, on average. Secondly, pharmacies were required to employ more than one pharmacist per shift. Another requirement was that the participating pharmacies should be located in one of three geographical regions (North, Central, and South). Furthermore, selected pharmacies needed to maintain readily accessible and reasonably complete prescription

records, whether in electronic or paper-based format, to facilitate efficient data collection. Finally, the willingness of pharmacy management and staff to participate in the study and grant access to prescription data was a crucial inclusion criterion, and the pharmacies also had to have operated within a region for a minimum of 6 months.

Pharmacies were first screened for eligibility based on these criteria. The researcher then contacted pharmacy owners or managers to explain the study's objectives, data collection process, and ethical considerations, including approval from the University of Petra's Research Ethics Committee. Those who expressed interest were invited to a follow-up meeting to discuss study expectations in detail. Written informed consent was obtained before participation.

During data collection, research pharmacists closely observed all prescriptions before documenting any intercepted PEs using the data collection form. Regular communication with participating pharmacies was maintained through site visits and a structured reporting system, ensuring compliance with study protocols and addressing any concerns.

Data collection and operational definitions

The data collection form encompassed multiple fields related to prescription processes and patient characteristics. These fields included date of data collection, type of pharmacy (chain or independent), number of staff per shift, degree of pharmacist in charge, years of experience, and highest degree obtained. In addition, the total number of patients per shift who received medications from each type of pharmacy (chain vs. independent) was recorded.

The form also contained fields related to PEs, including whether an error occurred (yes/no) and the type of error, such as wrong drug, dose, frequency, duration, or omission error. Error severity (minor, moderate, severe, or lethal) was recorded accordingly. Patient demographics, such as gender, age, and comorbidities, were also

recorded. These demographics were obtained from the prescription when available; otherwise, pharmacists collected the information directly from patients. Additionally, the form was designed to record whether the research pharmacist made any recommendations or interventions (yes/no), including process-based interventions (before the error reached the patient) and outcome-based ones (post-error interventions).

Finally, the form included fields related to patient outcomes that addressed patient acceptance of interventions (full/partial), physician acceptance (yes/no), clinical outcomes improvement (yes/no), hospitalization (yes/no), and death (yes/no). Pharmacists were instructed to follow up with patients for 1 week after the prescription was filled. This follow-up was necessary to evaluate the impact of pharmacist interventions on patient clinical outcomes. Follow-up involved direct communication with patients or their caregivers to assess symptom relief, chronic illness management, and achievement of specific health goals. Hospitalization data were collected by asking patients or caregivers whether hospital admission was required during the follow-up period, while mortality data were obtained from relatives or caregivers. Patient participation in follow-up was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained prior to data collection. In Jordan, pharmacist follow-up is not a standard part of routine care but was conducted in this study to assess the effectiveness of pharmacist interventions.

Data collection forms, including PE types and severity, were validated by the multidisciplinary expert committee to ensure correctness, completeness, and relevance. Prescribing errors were identified based on predefined criteria, and any disagreements were resolved through discussion within the committee.

The types and severity of PEs adopted in this study are listed in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The classification was adapted from the study by Dean et al. (2000), focusing on the most clinically relevant errors in primary care settings while maintaining alignment with established literature.

Table 1. Prescribing errors classification (Dean et al. 2001; Abdel-Qader et al. 2010).

Wrong drug	1- Prescribing a drug for a patient for whom, as a result of a co-existing clinical condition, that drug is contraindicated. 2- Prescription of a drug to which the patient has a documented clinically significant allergy. 3- Prescribing a drug for which there is no indication for that patient. 4- Duplication
Wrong dose	1- When the dose of a medicine recommended to be taken at a particular time is incorrect (overdosage or underdosage). 2- Prescribing a drug in a dose that, according to British National Formulary or data sheet recommendations, is inappropriate for the patient's renal function.
Wrong frequency	When the prescribed frequency of medicine is different from current evidence-based treatment guidelines
Wrong dosage form	When a dosage form not intended by the prescriber is written in the prescription, or when a dosage form is not available for the prescribed drug.
Omission	Omissions: Missing elements that will require further information. Major omissions would require the pharmacist to contact the prescriber. Minor omissions may be filled by the pharmacist based on professional judgment and additional information gathered from the patient or prescriber.
Pharmaceutical issues	Prescribing a drug to be given by intravenous infusion in a diluent that is incompatible with the drug prescribed Drugs interactions.

Table 2. The severity of prescribing errors (Overhage and Lukes 1999; Abdel-Qader et al. 2010).

Lethal error	1- High potential for life-threatening adverse effects/reactions. 2- The potentially lifesaving drug at a dosage too low for the disease being treated. 3- High dosage (>10 times normal) of a drug with a low therapeutic index.
Severe error	1- Route of administration could lead to severe toxicity 2- A low dosage of a drug for a serious disease in the patient with acute distress 3- High dosage (4–10 times normal) of a drug with a low therapeutic index 4- Dosage resulted in serum drug concentration in the potentially toxic range 5- The drug could exacerbate the patient's condition (related to warnings or contraindications) 6- Misspelling or mix-up in medication order could lead to dispensing of the wrong drug 7- Documented allergy to a drug 8- High dosage (>10 times normal) of a drug without a low therapeutic index
Moderate error	1- High dosage (1.5–4 times normal) of a drug with a low therapeutic index 2- Drug dosage too low for patient's condition 3- High dosage (1.5–10 times normal) of a drug without a low therapeutic index 4- Errant dual-drug therapy for a single condition 5- Inappropriate dosage interval 6- Omission from the medication order
Minor error	1- Incomplete information in the medication order 2- The unavailable or inappropriate dosage form 3- Non-formulary drug 4- Noncompliance with standard formulations and hospital policies
No error	1- Information or clarification requested by the physician or other healthcare professional from the pharmacist 2- Cost savings only

Data analysis

The data analysis was conducted with SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize and characterize the collected data, using measures such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations to account for relevant variables. To compare differences in categorical variables, the chi-square test was used. The t-test and ANOVA were used to compare means of continuous variables. A multivariable logistic regression model was used to assess the predictors of specific outcomes related to the study. All statistical analyses were performed at a predetermined level of significance ($p < 0.05$) to establish statistical significance of findings and were presented using appropriate tables, graphs, and measures that facilitate clear reporting.

Participating pharmacists received training on the data collection process to ensure completeness of the forms for all recruited patients; consequently, there were no missing data for the primary variables analyzed in this study.

Results

The total number of community pharmacies included in the study was 12, of which seven (58.3%) were chain pharmacies, eight (61.6%) had two pharmacists per shift, and half had 6–30 customers per shift (Table 3). In addition, three (25.0%) pharmacies were receiving more than 30 prescriptions and dispensing more than 50 medications per shift. The total number of pharmacists working in those pharmacies was 26, of which 21 (80.8%) had bachelor's degrees and 11 (42.3%) had 5–10 years of experience.

Table 3. Characteristics of pharmacies (N = 12) and pharmacists (N = 26) included in the study.

Parameter		Total, n (%)
Pharmacies		
Type of pharmacy	Independent	5 (41.6%)
	Chain	7 (58.3%)
Number of pharmacists per shift	2	8 (61.6%)
	3	2 (23.0%)
	4	1 (15.4%)
Years of opening	1–3	4 (33.3%)
	4–6	5 (41.6%)
	>6	3 (25.0%)
Number of customers per shift	5–15	2 (16.7%)
	16–30	6 (50.0%)
	>30	4 (33.3%)
Number of prescriptions per shift	5–15	2 (16.7%)
	16–30	7 (58.3%)
	>30	3 (25.0%)
Number of medications dispensed per shift	<30	2 (16.7%)
	30–50	7 (58.3%)
	>50	3 (25.0%)
Pharmacists		
The highest degree of pharmacist in charge	BSc	21 (80.8%)
	MSc/PharmD	5 (19.2%)
	PhD	0 (0.0%)
Years of experience	1–5	10 (38.5%)
	6–10	11 (42.3%)
	>10	5 (19.2%)

These characteristics provide context on factors influencing PEs and pharmacist interventions, ensuring alignment with established medication safety research.

In total, 617 patients were included in this study, of which 275 (44.6%) were aged between 25 and 35 years, and 27 (4.4%) were aged above 65 years (Table 4). Most of the patients were male, 431 (69.9%). In terms of comorbidities, 119 (19.2%) suffered from low back pain, 76 (12.3%) had diabetes, 65 (10.5%) had hypertension, and 48 (7.8%) had ischemic heart disease. The most common reasons for visiting the pharmacy were requesting an OTC medicine (452, 73.3%) and filling or refilling a prescription (314, 50.9%).

Table 4. Characteristics of patients included in the study (N = 617).

Parameter		Total, n (%)
Age (years)	16–24	153 (24.8%)
	25–35	275 (44.6%)
	36–65	162 (26.3%)
	>65	27 (4.4%)
Gender	Female	186 (30.1%)
	Male	431 (69.9%)
Comorbidities*	Ischemic heart disease	48 (7.8%)
	Diabetes mellitus	76 (12.3%)
	Hypertension	65 (10.5%)
	COPD	26 (4.2%)
	Asthma	49 (7.9%)
	Osteoarthritis	57 (9.2%)
	Depression	28 (4.5%)
	Low back pain	119 (19.2%)
	Cancer	5 (0.8%)
	ARI	49 (7.9%)
Other	27 (4.4%)	
Reason for pharmacy visit*	Prescription fill/refill	314 (50.9%)
	Request an OTC medication	452 (73.3%)
	Request health and wellness products	115 (18.6%)
	Health advice	84 (13.6%)
	Vaccination	56 (9.1%)
	Receiving an injection	49 (7.9%)

IHD: ischemic heart disease; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; ARI: acute respiratory infection. Comorbidities were documented through patient acknowledgment or by reviewing the medications requested. Health and wellness products included vitamins, supplements, skincare products, and personal care items. OTC: over the counter. *Multiple options could be selected for one participant.

Table 5 shows examples of PEs, their types, severity, and corresponding interventions conducted by pharmacists.

Of the 617 patients included in the study, 102 had PEs, with 165 erroneous medication orders. The total number of PEs was 192, including 49 omission errors. The incidence rates of PEs, patients with errors, and omission errors were 14.9%, 16.5%, and 4.0%, respectively (Table 6).

As shown in Fig. 1, 33 (32.4%) of the patients with errors had five medication orders in their prescriptions, six (5.9%) had six medication orders, and five (4.9%) had one medication order.

Of the 192 PEs, the most common type was wrong drug (33.33%), followed by omission errors (25.52%), wrong dose (17.19%), and wrong frequency (13.02%). The least common type was wrong duration (10.94%) (Table 7).

Of the 192 PEs identified, nine (4.69%) were deemed lethal, 42 (21.88%) severe, and 75 (39.06%) moderate. Minor errors accounted for 34.38% of the total PEs. There was no statistically significant difference in the severity of PEs across different medication classes ($p > 0.05$). The most common medications associated with severe errors were analgesics (19/42, 45.24%) and antibiotics (14/42, 33.33%). Of the nine lethal errors, three (33.33%) were related to antidiabetics, four (44.44%) to antihypertensives, and two (22.22%) to antivirals (Table 8).

There was no significant difference in the types of medications across erroneous and non-erroneous medication orders ($p = 0.091$) (Table 9). Overall, analgesics (21.4%), antibiotics (14.4%), and antidiabetics (13.8%) were the most commonly prescribed medications for patients with errors. The most common erroneous therapeutic category was antibiotics (24.8%), followed by analgesics (14.5%). The dosage forms of the medications were similar across erroneous and non-erroneous medication orders ($p = 0.106$). The most common dosage forms for patients with errors were tablets (55.7%), capsules (14.1%), and liquids (7.9%).

The total number of pharmacist interventions was 216, which included 144 (66.7%) that were process-based and 72 (33.3%) that were outcome-based. These interventions were organized into predefined categories to differentiate between those that specifically addressed PEs and those that provided general clinical recommendations. Among these interventions, 162 (75.0%) were fully accepted by patients, and 148 (68.5%) received full approval from physicians. Full acceptance by physicians was defined as the complete execution of the pharmacist's recommendation, whereas partial acceptance indicated alterations to the recommendation that were not carried out in their entirety.

Among the process-based pharmacist interventions, substitution of a prescribed drug (36, 25.0%), removal of a drug from the prescription (22, 15.3%), and adjusting the dose of a prescribed drug (14, 9.7%) were the most common. The least common process-based pharmacist interventions were advising the patient to stop smoking (eight, 5.6%) and advising the patient to exercise (six, 4.2%). Although these lifestyle suggestions were not directly related to PEs, they were incorporated as general advice for patient care. Adding a drug to the prescription (AOR: 0.7; 95% CI: 0.5–0.9) was considered less likely to enhance clinical outcomes in comparison to adjusting the dose of an existing medication (Table 10).

Among the outcome-based interventions, initiation of a new drug (23, 31.9%), adjusting the dose of a dispensed drug (17, 23.6%), and cessation of drug therapy (16, 22.2%) were the most common. Referral to a physician (4, 2.8%) was the least common intervention. Interventions related to the initiation of a new drug (AOR: 0.4; 95% CI: 0.2–0.7) were less likely to yield improvements in clinical outcomes when compared to the discontinuation of drug therapy.

As shown in Fig. 2, the significant predictors of PE occurrence were age above 65 years (AOR: 1.8; 95% CI: 1.4–2.9) and comorbidities (acute respiratory infections) (AOR: 2.8; 95% CI: 1.7–4.3).

Table 5. Clinical examples of prescribing errors.

Clinical scenario	Type of PEs	Severity of PEs	Pharmacist intervention
A 25-year-old patient with a known allergy to penicillin was prescribed a ceftriaxone injection.	Wrong drug	Lethal	Upon reviewing the patient's medical history and identifying the allergy, the pharmacist promptly contacted the prescriber to highlight the risk associated with the prescribed medication. The pharmacist emphasized the patient's allergy to penicillin and the potential for a severe allergic reaction to ceftriaxone. Subsequently, the pharmacist recommended an alternative antibiotic, azithromycin, which is not a beta-lactam antibiotic and thus poses no cross-reactivity for patients with penicillin allergies. The prescriber agreed with the recommendation, and the medication was changed to azithromycin.
A 43-year-old patient refilled diclofenac sodium tablets at a dosage of 75 mg to be taken three times per day.	Wrong frequency	Moderate	The pharmacist, upon noticing the unusually high frequency of administration, contacted the prescribing physician to discuss the potential risks associated with such a regimen. The pharmacist suggested modifying the prescription to a more conventional frequency, recommending that diclofenac be taken twice a day instead of three times. This change aimed to reduce the risk of adverse effects while maintaining therapeutic efficacy. The physician was informed about the standard dosing guidelines and the potential risks of gastrointestinal, renal, and cardiovascular side effects associated with higher dosing frequencies of NSAIDs like diclofenac.
A 68-year-old patient suffering from a headache was prescribed paracetamol with no dose in the prescription.	Omission	Minor	The pharmacist instructed the patient to take one tablet (500 mg) twice daily as needed, with a maximum of 4 grams per day.
A 21-year-old patient with a history of asthma and a recent asthmatic attack was prescribed propranolol.	Wrong drug	Severe	Contacted the physician to inform her about the issue and suggested a selective beta blocker, with monitoring of the patient.
A 50-year-old patient with a history of severe renal impairment was prescribed metformin.	Wrong drug	Severe	Did not dispense and contacted the physician.

Table 6. Calculation of cumulative incidence of prescribing errors.

Code	Variable	Equation	Value
A	Total number of patients during the study	–	617
B	Total number of medication orders (based on prescriptions)	–	1238
C	Total number of omission errors	–	49
D	Total number of patients with errors	–	102
E	One prescribing error	–	146
F	Two prescribing errors	–	11
G	Three prescribing errors	–	8
H	Total number of erroneous medication orders intercepted by pharmacists	E+F+G	165
I	Total number of prescribing errors	E+2F+3G	192
J	Cumulative incidence of patients with error	(D/A) × 100%	16.5%
K	Cumulative incidence with prescribing errors	I/(B+C) × 100%	14.9%
L	Cumulative incidence of erroneous orders	H/(B+C) × 100%	12.8%
M	Cumulative incidence of omission errors	(C/B) × 100%	4.0%
N	Cumulative incidence of prescribing errors without omission errors	{(I – C)/B} × 100%	11.6%
O	Cumulative incidence of prescribing errors vs. opportunities for errors	I/4(B+C) × 100%	3.7%

Discussion

Prescribing errors (PEs) are an increasingly serious patient safety threat in both primary and secondary health-care settings. Nonetheless, while PEs in hospitals have received greater consideration than those in primary care, PEs in primary care – where millions of prescriptions are filled annually – remain poorly understood. In addition,

the role of pharmacists in preventing such errors has rarely been addressed; thus, this study sought to examine PE incidence, types, severity, predictors, and interventions performed by community pharmacists to reduce them across Jordan.

To achieve this aim, a direct observational approach was utilized in 12 community pharmacies in Jordan. Specifically, an extensive literature review and input from a

Figure 1. Number of patients with errors vs. number of medication orders.

Table 7. Types of prescribing errors identified (N = 192).

Type of PEs	Frequency (%)
Wrong drug	64 (33.33%)
Omission errors	49 (25.52%)
Wrong dose	33 (17.19%)
Wrong frequency	25 (13.02%)
Wrong duration	21 (10.94%)

Table 8. Severity of prescribing errors (N = 192).

Severity of PEs	Frequency (%)
Lethal	9 (4.69%)
Minor	66 (34.38%)
Severe	42 (21.88%)
Moderate	75 (39.06%)

panel of experts were used for the development of the data collection form, which was rigorously validated. This research approach included two notable strengths. Firstly, the use of operational definitions that describe the characteristics of severity and type of PEs. This classification system was adopted from previous studies (Overhage and Lukes 1999; Abdel-Qader et al. 2010). A severity scale based on Overhage and Lukes (1999) was applied. Equal clarity and consistency were provided by operational definitions in terms of measurement and classification of variables, so that readers understood and interpreted them similarly. Secondly, the incidence rates of PEs were calculated by means of specific equations adapted from the study by Abdel-Qader et al. (2010). Using these equations ensured consistency, validity, and transparency in the calculations, which enabled comparisons and results that were meaningful and reliable. Overall, this research addressed the gap in knowledge by providing new insight into the incidence, types, and severity of PEs in primary care in Jordan and the role of pharmacists in preventing errors. Additionally, its outcomes could be used for improving patient safety as well as developing pharmacy practice and health policies in other settings worldwide.

In this study, more than half of the pharmacies were chain pharmacies. Standardized procedures and centralized systems in chain pharmacies may foster more consistent error-prevention strategies compared to independent pharmacies (Miller and Goodman 2017). Regarding staffing, the majority of pharmacies (61.6%) had two pharmacists per shift. This staffing model, a criterion for inclusion, was intended to provide a reasonable pharmacist-to-patient ratio, ensuring adequate time for patient counseling and the detection of potential errors. In our study, PE incidence was 14.9%, which was higher than the reported incidence of PEs (12.5%) in the emergency department of the largest public hospital in Jordan (Abdel-Qader et al. 2020a). A number of factors might have contributed to this higher PE incidence in community pharmacies. First, no electronic health record (EHR) system is in place to provide continuity between physicians in primary care and community pharmacies. In a systematic review, Ammenwerth et al. (2008) reported that EHR can reduce the risk of medication error by up to 98%. An integrated EHR with electronic prescribing can eliminate errors from illegible handwriting and provide pharmacists with instant access to patient medication history, allergies, and potential drug interactions, thereby strengthening clinical decision-making and collaboration between prescribers and pharmacists (Gandhi et al. 2005). Second, the lack of regulatory oversight and auditing specifically focused on physicians contributes to the challenge. Studies have shown that hospital settings generally have more structured mechanisms for detecting and addressing PEs due to dedicated quality improvement teams and established reporting systems (Vira et al. 2006). In contrast, primary care settings, which consist of multiple independent physicians or small clinics, face difficulties in implementing standardized protocols and maintaining consistent oversight. The hierarchical structure of hospitals allows for systematic monitoring and corrective actions, whereas primary care practices often have limited personnel and resources specifically allocated for monitoring PEs (Gandhi et al. 2005).

Table 9. Characteristics of medication orders (N = 1238).

Types of medications	Total, n (%)	Erroneous (N = 165), n (%)	P-value
Analgesics	265 (21.4%)	24 (14.5%)	0.091
Antibiotics	178 (14.4%)	41 (24.8%)	
Antidiabetics	171 (13.8%)	14 (8.5%)	
Antihypertensives	156 (12.6%)	12 (7.3%)	
Anti-inflammatory	83 (6.7%)	9 (5.5%)	
Antihistamines	68 (5.5%)	9 (5.5%)	
H2 Blockers	51 (4.1%)	6 (3.6%)	
Antihyperlipidemics	48 (3.9%)	8 (4.8%)	
Antitussives	48 (3.9%)	7 (4.2%)	
Antifungals	36 (2.9%)	2 (1.2%)	
Antispasmodics	31 (2.5%)	4 (2.4%)	
Antivirals	27 (2.2%)	6 (3.6%)	
Antidiarrheals	22 (1.8%)	3 (1.8%)	
Vitamins	17 (1.4%)	8 (4.8%)	
Antigout agents	11 (0.9%)	5 (3.0%)	
Antihyperuricemics	9 (0.7%)	2 (1.2%)	
Antimalarials	6 (0.5%)	3 (1.8%)	
Other	11 (0.9%)	2 (1.2%)	
Dosage Forms			0.106
Tablets	689 (55.7%)	55 (33.3%)	
Capsules	174 (14.1%)	36 (21.8%)	
Liquids	98 (7.9%)	21 (12.7%)	
Topicals	59 (4.8%)	13 (7.9%)	
Suppositories	66 (5.3%)	10 (6.1%)	
Inhalers	54 (4.4%)	11 (6.7%)	
Injectables	63 (5.1%)	13 (7.9%)	
Lozenges	35 (2.8%)	6 (3.6%)	

Table 10. Types of pharmacist interventions and predictors of clinical outcomes.

Parameter	Total, n (%)	Improvement in clinical outcomes	Worsening in clinical outcomes	Predicting improvement in clinical outcomes, AOR (95% CI)
Process-based pharmacist interventions				
Adjusting the dose of a prescribed drug (Ref)	14 (9.7%)	9 (10.11%)	5 (9.1%)	1.00
Substitution of a prescribed drug	36 (25%)	23 (25.8%)	13 (23.6%)	1.1 (0.5–1.9)
Adjusting the duration of a prescribed drug	11 (7.6%)	7 (7.9%)	4 (7.3%)	1.5 (0.7–3.4)
Adding a drug to the prescription	16 (11.1%)	9 (10.11%)	7 (12.7%)	0.7 (0.5–0.9)
Removing a drug from the prescription	22 (15.3%)	14 (15.7%)	8 (14.5%)	2.5 (1.4–5.7)
Psychological support	9 (6.2%)	5 (5.6%)	4 (7.3%)	0.8 (0.5–1.3)
Patient education about medication use	15 (10.4%)	10 (11.2%)	5 (9.1%)	1.8 (0.7–5.1)
Advising the patient to eat healthy food	7 (4.9%)	6 (6.7%)	1 (1.8%)	1.4 (0.7–2.4)
Advising the patient to stop smoking	8 (5.6%)	3 (3.3%)	5 (9.1%)	1.2 (0.4–1.8)
Advising the patient to do exercise	6 (4.2%)	3 (3.4%)	3 (5.5%)	0.6 (0.3–4.1)
Outcome-based interventions				
Cessation of drug therapy (Ref)	16 (22.2%)	10 (22.2%)	6 (22.2%)	1.00
Initiation of a new drug	23 (31.9%)	12 (26.7%)	11 (40.7%)	0.4 (0.2–0.7)
Adjusting the dose of a dispensed drug	17 (23.6%)	11 (24.4%)	6 (22.2%)	3.1 (0.8–7.6)
Recommending a laboratory test	13 (18.1%)	10 (22.2%)	3 (11.1%)	1.9 (0.8–4.5)
Referral to physician	3 (4.2%)	2 (4.4%)	1 (3.7%)	0.9 (0.7–1.7)

Ref: reference; CI: confidence interval; AOR: adjusted odds ratio. Bold adjusted odds ratio indicates significant findings. Parameters are described as proportions [n (%)] unless stated otherwise.

The role of PEs in primary care has been studied in several research settings. In Saudi Arabia, the incidence of PEs in primary care was higher (18.7%) than the rate in our

study (Khoja et al. 2011). However, in the UK, a lower incidence of PEs (5%) was reported among primary care providers (Avery 2013). Moreover, PEs were also identified in

Figure 2. Predictors of prescribing error occurrence.

primary care in Australia (Koper et al. 2013). The different approaches used to calculate the incidence of PEs, variation in healthcare practices, medication management systems, reporting mechanisms, and cultural factors affecting patient safety contributed to these diverse reports across countries.

In our research, we found that the most frequent PEs were wrong drug and omission errors. This coincides with the results of other research studies in different countries, including Jordan (Abdel-Qader et al. 2020a), the UK (Abdel-Qader et al. 2010; Avery 2013; Ashcroft et al. 2015), and Ethiopia (Simegn et al. 2022). In Jordan, wrong drug and omission errors were the most common PEs in the emergency department (Abdel-Qader et al. 2020a). In the UK, omission errors were frequently identified in primary care (Avery 2013). Simegn et al. (2022) found that omission and wrong drug errors were the most frequently reported by community pharmacists. In comparison, a prospective study by Stasiak et al. (2014) conducted in the emergency department reported that wrong dose was the most common type of PE.

The occurrence of wrong drug and omission errors at high rates could be attributed to several factors. First, insufficient information is often available for accurate medication prescribing. Physicians in primary care may not have access to relevant patient information, such as medical history, allergies, or concurrent medications. Furthermore, differences in guidelines and professional opinions regarding what medication should be prescribed can increase these types of errors. Physicians may encounter confusion due to multiple guidelines regarding a given condition or medication. They may also have different interpretations or preferences when prescribing certain drugs, leading to inconsistent practices and potentially resulting in PEs.

In our study, the most common erroneous therapeutic categories were antibiotics and analgesics. Our findings aligned with the Ethiopian study (Simegn et al. 2022). However, in the UK, anticoagulants, opioid analgesics, and insulin were the most frequent erroneous medica-

tions in primary care (Cousins et al. 2019). These findings do not necessarily mean that these medicines are naturally prone to errors but rather reflect the prescribing patterns within each respective location and healthcare setting.

Most of the PEs in our study were either moderate or minor in severity. Nonetheless, about one-fifth of the PEs reported were severe. It was not possible to compare our results with other studies because they used different methodologies to measure severity. For example, a UK study used an index or scale rating method for PE severity evaluation; severity grading showed that 41.1% of PEs were minor, 51.6% significant, and the remaining 7.3% serious or potentially life-threatening (Koper et al. 2013). Overall, PEs pose a serious threat to patient safety in both primary and secondary care.

This study expanded the notion that patient characteristics could be important predictors of PEs. Elderly patients (age >65 years; AOR: 1.8; 95% CI: 1.4–2.9) and those with acute respiratory infections (ARI) (AOR: 2.8; 95% CI: 1.7–4.3) were at higher risk of experiencing PEs. Elderly patients usually have multiple chronic conditions that can be aggravated by polypharmacy. Several studies (Abdel-Qader et al. 2020c; Kua et al. 2021; Vinks et al. 2006) found that polypharmacy increases the risk of PEs as well. The association between ARIs and PE risk may be explained by several factors. A possible factor is the insufficient up-to-date information that physicians possessed concerning respiratory infections. Medical knowledge and guidelines for the evaluation and management of ARIs are evolving continuously. Therefore, physicians who were not up to date on these guidelines could unknowingly prescribe treatment based on outdated information. Moreover, the indiscriminate use of antibiotics for ARIs without culture or laboratory testing is a common practice in Jordan. Some patients believe that antibiotics should be prescribed for every type of respiratory symptom without laboratory confirmation, resulting in a high rate of unnecessary treatment and addi-

tional health risks. Furthermore, not having the resources to perform more testing at the point of primary care to support the decision to use antibiotics may have contributed to this association between ARIs and PE risk.

Our study examined personalized pharmacist interventions, patient acceptance, and physician approval, including whether certain approaches resulted in clinical improvement. Results of our analysis revealed 216 pharmacist interventions, of which 66.7% were process-based and 33.3% outcome-based. All initiatives demonstrated a positive effect on patient care, as reflected in the high percentage of approval by patients (75.0%) and physicians (68.5%). This evidence clearly highlighted the pharmacists' contribution to care optimization and to reducing PEs. Additionally, we discovered that adjusting the dose of a prescribed medicine, rather than adding a new drug to the regimen, was more likely to be associated with a positive outcome. Specifically, adding a new drug to the prescription (AOR: 0.7; 95% CI: 0.5–0.9) was less likely to enhance clinical outcomes compared to dose adjustment (the reference category). Intriguingly, our study demonstrated that initiating new medications was associated with worse clinical improvements compared to discontinuing therapy altogether (AOR: 0.4; 95% CI: 0.2–0.7 for initiation vs. cessation of therapy). This finding highlighted the importance of careful consideration when initiating new medications, emphasizing the need for evidence-based decision-making and weighing potential benefits against risks. It also underscored the necessity of deprescribing and discontinuing drugs that have no current indication or may have negative consequences.

The role of community pharmacists in preventing PEs is not new. Notably, Rupp et al. (1992) prospectively monitored interventions performed by 89 retail pharmacists from across the US nearly three decades ago. Among the total of 33,011 medication orders observed, only 1.9% of the cases were affected by pharmacist interventions. Interestingly, the problems identified by pharmacists in that study accounted for as much as 28.3% that would have been potentially harmful to patients without pharmacist interventions. Several other studies have also highlighted widespread pharmacist participation in the prevention of PEs. A Korean study (Han et al. 2023) showed that community pharmacists succeeded in preventing 88% of PEs in primary care. A healthcare center in Saudi Arabia conducted a 3-month survey in which more than 1500 patients were saved from PEs (Alzahrani et al. 2021); most of these interventions were dose adjustments.

Overall, PEs in primary care were common and could cause severe harm. This study addressed a knowledge gap by investigating PEs intercepted in Jordanian primary care. The high incidence of PEs indicated the need for interventions to enhance prescribing practices, emphasizing pharmacist involvement in error prevention as well as patient characteristics as predictors for PEs. The findings of this research had key implications for patient safety improvements, pharmacy practice, and health policy development worldwide. These findings underscore the need for systemic interventions beyond individual pharmacy practice. Policymakers in Jordan should consider the development and implementation of a national electronic prescribing

system to bridge the information gap between prescribers and pharmacists. Furthermore, establishing mandatory continuing professional development (CPD) modules for physicians, focusing on common PE types such as wrong drug and omission errors, could directly address the root causes identified in this study. Formalizing communication protocols between primary care clinics and community pharmacies could also empower pharmacists to resolve potential errors more efficiently, ultimately enhancing patient safety on a national scale. Future research should focus on interventions to reduce PEs and enhance prescribing practices in primary care settings worldwide.

The findings of this study need to be interpreted in the context of its limitations. First, the self-reporting nature of the study could have introduced bias, as pharmacists might not have reported all PEs and their interventions. To minimize this, we excluded pharmacies with only one pharmacist in charge to avoid time constraints. Second, this was not a study based on random sampling, which might have affected the generalizability of the findings. However, in addition to calculating the appropriate sample size, researchers purposively selected pharmacies that represented different locations and sizes across Jordan; hence, this could still provide valid findings.

Conclusion

PEs were common in primary care in Jordan. In this study, 102 out of 617 patients experienced PEs. Most of these errors were wrong drug, omission, and wrong dose. Around one-fifth of the errors were deemed severe. The most commonly prescribed therapeutic categories for patients with errors were analgesics, antibiotics, and antidiabetics. Pharmacists conducted both process-based and outcome-based interventions. The most common process-based pharmacist interventions were substituting a prescribed drug, removing a drug from the prescription, and adjusting the dose of a prescribed drug. Adding a drug to the prescription was less likely to result in improvements compared to adjusting the dose. Among the outcome-based interventions, initiating a new drug, adjusting the dose of a dispensed drug, and ceasing drug therapy were the most common, while referring to a physician was the least common. Initiating a new drug was less likely to lead to improvements compared to ceasing drug therapy. Age and comorbidities were significant predictors of PEs.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: DQ, Data curation: SO, Formal analysis: KK, Funding acquisition: DQ, Investigation: ET, Methodology: ET,

Project administration: NM, RI, Resources: RI, Software: RI, Supervision: DQ, Validation: SH, Visualization: DQ, Writing – original draft: SO, SJ, AS, Writing – review and editing: DQ, SO, SJ, AS.

Author ORCIDs

Derar H. Abdel-Qader <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2576-4464>

Shorouq Al-Omouh <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1154-1509>

Esra' Taybeh <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7493-7865>

Nadia Al Mazrouei <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1339-9730>

Rana Ibrahim <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9104-3852>

Salim Hamadi <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2534-7900>

Sahar Jaradat <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3769-4088>

Alia Saleh <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5772-2714>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Abdel-Qader DH, Al Meslamani AZ, El-Shara' AA, Ismael NS, Albassam A, Lewis PJ, Hamadi S, Abbas HS, Al Mazrouei N, Ibrahim OM (2020a) Investigating prescribing errors in the emergency department of a large governmental hospital in Jordan. *Journal of Pharmacy and Health Services Research* 11(4): 375–382. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jphs.12376>
- Abdel-Qader DH, Saadi Ismael N, Al Meslamani AZ, Albassam A, El-Shara' AA, Lewis PJ, Hamadi S, Al Mazrouei N (2020b) The Role of Clinical Pharmacy in Preventing Prescribing Errors in the Emergency Department of a Governmental Hospital in Jordan: A Pre-Post Study. *Hospital Pharmacy*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018578720942231>
- Abdel-Qader DH, Al Meslamani AZ, Lewis PJ, Hamadi S (2020c) Incidence, nature, severity, and causes of dispensing errors in community pharmacies in Jordan. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 43: 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-020-01126-w>
- Abdel-Qader DH, Harper L, Cantrill JA, Tully MP (2010) Pharmacists' interventions in prescribing errors at hospital discharge. *Drug Safety* 33(11): 1027–1044. <https://doi.org/10.11538310-000000000-00000>
- Alzahrani AA, Alwhaibi MM, Asiri YA, Kamal KM, Alhawassi TM (2021) Description of pharmacists' reported interventions to prevent prescribing errors among in hospital inpatients: a cross sectional retrospective study. *BMC Health Services Research* 21(1): 432. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-06418-z>
- Ammenwerth E, Schnell-Inderst P, Machan C, Siebert U (2008) The Effect of Electronic Prescribing on Medication Errors and Adverse Drug Events: A Systematic Review. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 15(5): 585–600. <https://doi.org/10.1197/jamia.M2667>
- Ashcroft DM, Lewis PJ, Tully MP, Farragher TM, Taylor D, Wass V, Williams SD, Dornan T (2015) Prevalence, nature, severity, and risk factors for prescribing errors in hospital inpatients: A prospective study in 20 UK hospitals. *Drug Safety* 38(9): 833–843. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40264-015-0320-x>
- Avery T (2013) Investigating the prevalence and causes of prescribing errors in general practice: The PRACtICE Study. *British Journal of General Practice* 63(613): e543–e553. <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp13X670679>
- Basheti IA, Nassar R, Barakat M, Alqudah R, Abufarha R, Mukattash TL, Saini B (2021) Pharmacists' readiness to deal with the coronavirus pandemic: Assessing awareness and perception of roles. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 17(3): 514–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2020.04.020>
- Cousins D, Crompton A, Harris W, Dewsbury C (2019) The top ten prescribing errors in practice and how to avoid them. *The Pharmaceutical Journal* 302: 7922. <https://pharmaceutical-journal.com/article/ld/the-top-ten-prescribing-errors-in-practice-and-how-to-avoid-them>
- Dean B, Barber N, Schachter M (2000) What is a prescribing error? *Quality in Health Care* 9(4): 232–237. <https://doi.org/10.1136/qhc.9.4.232>
- Gandhi TK, Weingart SN, Seger AC, Borus J, Burdick E, Poon EG, Leape LL, Bates DW (2005) Outpatient prescribing errors and the impact of computerized prescribing. *Journal of General Internal Medicine* 20(9): 837–841. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1525-1497.2005.0194.x>
- Han J-H, Heo K-N, Han J, Lee M-S, Kim S-J, Min S, Ah Y-M, Lee J-Y (2023) Analysis of Medication Errors Reported by Community Pharmacists in the Republic of Korea: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Medicina (Kaunas)* 59(1): 151. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina59010151>
- Khoja T, Neyaz Y, Quresh NA, Mogzoub MA, Haycox A, Walley T (2011) Medication errors in primary care in Riyadh city, Saudi Arabia. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal* 17(2): 156–159. <https://doi.org/10.26719/2011.17.2.156>
- Koper D, Kamenski G, Flamm M, Böhmendorfer B, Sönnichsen A (2013) Frequency of medication errors in primary care patients with polypharmacy. *Family Practice* 30(3): 313–319. <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cms070>
- Kua C-H, Yeo CYY, Tan PC, Char CWT, Tan CWY, Mak V, Leong IY-O, Lee SWH (2021) Association of Deprescribing With Reduction in Mortality and Hospitalization: A Pragmatic Stepped-Wedge Cluster-Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association* 22(1): 82–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamda.2020.03.012>
- Miller R, Goodman C (2017) Do chain pharmacies perform better than independent pharmacies? Evidence from a standardised patient study of the management of childhood diarrhoea and suspected tuberculosis in urban India. *BMJ Global Health* 2(3): e000457. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2017-000457>
- Overhage JM, Lukes A (1999) Practical, reliable, comprehensive method for characterizing pharmacists' clinical activities. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy* 56(23): 2444–2450. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajhp/56.23.2444>

- Rupp MT, DeYoung M, Schondelmeyer SW (1992) Prescribing Problems and Pharmacist Interventions in Community Practice. *Medical Care* 30(10): 926–940. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005650-199210000-00005>
- Simegn W, Weldegerima B, Seid M, Zewdie A, Wondimsiegn D, Abyu C, Kasahun AE, Seid AM, Sisay G, Yeshaw Y (2022) Assessment of prescribing errors reported by community pharmacy professionals. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice* 15(1): 62. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-022-00461-9>
- Stasiak P, Afilalo M, Castelino T, Xue X, Colacone A, Soucy N, Dankoff J (2014) Detection and correction of prescription errors by an emergency department pharmacy service. *Canadian Journal of Emergency Medicine* 16(3): 193–206. <https://doi.org/10.2310/8000.2013.130975>
- Vinks THAM, de Koning FHP, de Lange TM, Egberts TCG (2006) Identification of potential drug-related problems in the elderly: the role of the community pharmacist. *Pharmacy World & Science* 28(1): 33–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-005-4213-4>
- Vira T, Colquhoun M, Etchells E (2006) Reconcilable differences: correcting medication errors at hospital admission and discharge. *BMJ Quality & Safety* 15(2): 122–126. <https://doi.org/10.1136/qshc.2005.015347>